

that short-duration line for eight generations. A new CMS line was named Zaoxian A in 1989.

Zaoxian A is still classified as a WA type. It is semidwarf (68 cm tall), averages 104 spikelets/panicle, with a 1,000-grain weight of 26.0 g. It also has long (1.62 m), well-exserted (73.5%) stigma, and its outcrossing rate is high (55.3%).

In 1990, we crossed Zaoxian A with three long-duration restorer lines, and tested yield capacity in a field experiment in Chengdu. Plots (2.5 m²) were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

The period to heading of F₁s related to Zaoxian A was about 20 d shorter than those of the restorer lines and shorter than the mid-parent values (see table). The period to heading of F₁s related to other CMS lines was about 10 d longer than the mid-parent values and longer than those of the restorer lines.

Days to heading of CMS lines, restorer lines, and F₁s, and growth duration and grain yield of F₁s.^a

Hybrid combination	Days to heading				Growth duration (d)	t/ha	Grain yield		
	P ₁	P ₂	Mid-parent value	F ₁			Percentage compared to		
							Check 1	Check 2	Check 3
Zaoxian A/R ₁	78	111	94.5	90	127	9.6	112	121	113
Zaoxian A/R ₂	78	113	95.5	92	128	9.4	110	119	111
Zaoxian A/R ₃	78	115	96.5	92	128	9.2	108	116	108
Zhen Shan 97 A/R ₁ (check 1)	75	111	93.0	112	148	8.6	100		
Zhen Shan 97 A/R ₄ (check 2)	75	88	81.5	92	130	8.0		100	
V20 A/R ₅ (check 3)	75	87	81.0	90	127	8.5			100

^aR₁ = Minghui 63, R₂ = 086, R₃ = Mingdian 501, R₄ = Zhalyeqing 8, R₅ = Ce 64. P₁ = CMS line, P₂ = restorer line. Check 1 and check 3 are the national checks of China and check 2 is the provincial check of Sichuan Province in the regional test of hybrid rice.

This indicates that days to heading of restorer lines is dominant over that of CMS lines Zhenshan 97 A and V20 A. Days to heading of Zaoxian A was incompletely dominant over that of the restorer lines.

Grain yields of hybrid combinations derived from Zaoxian A were higher than yields of national check Shanyou 63, although hybrid growth durations were

about 20 d shorter than that of Shanyou 63. Yields were significantly higher than those of Shanzhai 8 and Weiyou 64, which had almost the same growth durations as the hybrids.

The short duration of Zaoxian A appears to be incompletely dominant over the long duration of restorer lines, making Zaoxian A valuable for rice production and for hybrid rice breeding. □

Natural outcrossing on two cytoplasmic male sterile lines in northern India

J. S. Bijral, T. R. Sharma, B. B. Gupta, K. Singh, and C. L. Raina, SKUAST, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), R.S. Pura 181102, India

We studied the extent of outcrossing in cytoplasmic male sterile (A) lines RR988 A and RR39 A (CMS-WA cytoplasm developed at Pura, Jammu, and Kashmir). The cytosterile lines were surrounded by a single row of their

Seed set on 2 cytosterile lines at RARS, R.S. Pura, India, 1989 wet season.

A line	B line	Planting ratio	Grains/panicle (no.)		Total grains (no.)	Mean seed set (%)
			Filled	Unfilled		
RR988 A	CH988	1:1	68	850	918	7.4
RR39 A	K39	1:1	142	1101	1243	11.0

respective maintainer (B) lines (CH988 and K39). Plant spacing was 20 × 30 cm.

To synchronize flowering and prolong the pollen supply, maintainer lines were seeded 3 d earlier and 4 d later than the cytosterile (A) lines. All lines were transplanted at the same time, at 2 seedlings/hill. The flag leaves of the

cytosterile lines were not clipped.

The main panicles of 10 randomly selected plants of each cytosterile line were harvested individually and filled and unfilled grains/panicle counted. Outcrossing rate was low, probably because of poor panicle exertion of cytosterile lines (see table). □

Yield potential

Screening rice varieties and breeding lines for internode elongation ability under field conditions

R. V. Singh, Crop Research Station (CRS), Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, Uttar Pradesh (UP); J. L. Dwivedi (present address: Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division, IIRI); and O. P. Verma, CRS, Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, UP, India

We evaluated 155 varieties and experimental lines for internode elongation ability under field conditions. Entries were seeded 13 Apr 1989 in two 5-m rows, 25 cm apart.

Water depth reached 190 cm the first week of Oct. Plant height, number and length of internodes, kneeling ability, maturity, and phenotypic acceptability were observed. Maximum length of three consecutive elongated internodes was derived from the sums of three adjacent internodes.

Seventy-four entries failed to produce grain. Among surviving entries, 17 produced 9-12 internodes, with total internode lengths of 126-215 cm (see table). These lines also had much better kneeling ability.

Maturity ranged from the last week of Nov to the first week of Dec. Locally popular variety Jalmagna matured the first week of Dec, 233 d after seeding.

While Jalmagna was highest in total internode elongation, four other entries exceeded its maximum three consecutive